

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ANATOMY, MORPHOLOGY, AND PHYSIOLOGY OF PLANTS WITH RESPECT TO THEIR ABILITY TO TOLERATE DROUGHT CONDITIONS

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Abstract

One significant abiotic stressor that negatively affects plant growth, yield, and survival in a variety of habitats is drought. Investigating how plants adapt to water constraint has become crucial as climate change increases the frequency and severity of droughts globally. The structural, morphological, and physiological adaptations that allow plants to withstand dry conditions are thoroughly compared in this article. Reduced leaf area, thick waxy cuticles, deep or broad root systems, and modified shoot architecture are examples of morphological changes that aid in water conservation and enhance soil absorption. Particularly in xerophytic species and drought-tolerant crops, anatomical changes such as sunken or fewer stomata, compact mesophyll, stronger epidermal layers, and improved vascular tissues provide internal support and water retention. Under water stress, plants use a variety of physiological tactics to preserve cellular function. The accumulation of suitable solutes such as proline and soluble carbohydrates allows for osmotic adjustment; hormones regulate stomatal closure, particularly through abscisic acid; antioxidant enzymes are activated to prevent oxidative damage; and stress-responsive genes are expressed. In order to maximize water use in arid environments, certain plants also embrace more water-efficient photosynthetic pathways, such C4 or CAM metabolism. This analysis highlights the ways in which a mix of structural and physiological features contribute to effective drought tolerance by assessing several plant species, ranging from genetically modified crops to naturally drought-adapted desert flora. Combining these characteristics offers chances for crop development through breeding and biotechnology in addition to assisting survival

in harsh settings. In areas where drought is becoming more prevalent, a fuller comprehension of these systems is essential to the development of sustainable agricultural techniques.

INTRODUCTION

Crop output and global food security are greatly impacted by drought, one of the most important abiotic variables limiting agricultural productivity (Khan et al., 2013; Escalona et al., 1999). Drought disrupts overall plant metabolism by interfering with physiological functions like respiration, photosynthesis, and stomatal function, making it a major stressor in plant development. Plants respond to water deficiency by undergoing morphological and anatomical changes, producing hormones and osmotic regulators, and activating genes that respond to drought (Li et al., 2020; Anjum et al., 2017). Many research has looked at the morphological, biochemical, and physiological changes that occur in plants during drought in order to gain a better understanding of the mechanisms underlying drought resistance. Among these are the functions of molecular regulatory pathways and internal signal transduction systems (Misra et al., 2020). Signalling

molecules such as abscisic acid (ABA), calcium ions (Ca²⁺), inositol-1,4,5-triphosphate (IP₃), cyclic ADP-ribose (cADPR), and nitric oxide (NO) are used by plants to detect water shortfall under drought stress. These molecules then set off downstream signaling cascades (Patmi et al., 2020).

Certain genes are upregulated and physiological and morphological alterations are the outcomes of these cascades. Cellular defence and water retention are improved by functional gene products such proline, glycine betaine, soluble carbohydrates, late embryogenesis abundant (LEA) proteins, and aquaporins (Werner et al., 1999). Plant resilience in arid settings is enhanced by transcription factors such as CDPKs, MAPKs, HD-Zip/bZIP, AP2/ERF, NAC, MYB, and WRKY, which regulate gene expression implicated in drought stress responses (Taiz & Zeiger, 2015).

Figure 1. The process of plant drought-tolerance development.

The first is how drought stress affects a plant's internal structure and exterior shape. The physiological and biochemical reactions are explained in detail in the second section from the viewpoints of reactive oxygen metabolism, drought-induced protein metabolism, and osmotic regulation metabolism. Here, we provide

a brief overview of the production and scavenging of reactive oxygen species (ROS) as well as a list of key significant chemicals that regulate drought (Taiz & Zeiger, 2015).

The signal transduction pathway in plants makes up the third section. We explain intracellular signal

transduction pathways and provide detailed descriptions of common signals. The molecular control mechanism of plants is covered in the fourth section. Genes are used to summarize the anabolism and regulation processes of substances linked to osmotic control, drought-induced proteins, substances associated to signalling pathways, and transcription factors, respectively. All of the developments show how important it is to investigate how drought stress affects plants and how drought tolerance works (Taiz & Zeiger, 2015).

Stress is a changed physiological state brought on by things that have a tendency to throw things out of balance. Any physical or chemical alteration brought on by stress is referred to as strain (Gaspar et al., 2002).

EFFECTS OF DROUGHT ON PLANTS

At every stage of plant growth when there is a water deficit, the consequences of drought are visible, ranging from morphological to molecular levels. Plants react to environmental stressors in a multitude of ways, from altered cellular metabolism and gene expression to modifications in growth and production.

MORPHOLOGICAL RESPONSES

Growth

A thorough grasp of the mechanisms underlying crop growth and development is necessary to modify agronomic methods and ensure that food supply keep up with population increase. The intricate relationship between the sources and sink constraints of a plant's two primary organs—the root system and the shoot system—builds functional balance and determines plant growth. More than any other environmental condition, a persistent or temporary water deficiency is crucial to the growth and development of plants. According to Harris et al. (2002), the primary consequences of drought are poor establishment and botched germination. According to reports, drought stress significantly lowers seedling and sprouting (Kaya et al., 2006).

Cell division, expansion, and differentiation are the processes that define growth, which also entails intricate relationships between genetic, physiological, ecological, biochemical, and morphological events. These instances, which are impacted by water stress,

determine the type and amount of plant development. Because of the decrease in turgor pressure, cell growth is the physiological process most susceptible to dryness (Taiz and Zeiger, 2006).

Growth is the result of meristematic cell divisions producing daughter cells and the young cells' subsequent tremendous expansion. When higher plants experience severe water shortages, the supply of water from the xylem to the fencing elongating cells can be disrupted, which inhibits cell elongation (Nonami, 1998). Cell elongation and expansion caused by drought led to vitiated mitosis and decreased growth (Hussain et al., 2008).

Yield and related traits

Drought stress is a common occurrence for plants and lowers food yields globally. According to Rollins et al. (2013), the combined effects of heat and drought have a greater impact on crop productivity than each stress alone. Because the time and severity of the stress interact with the developmental processes that affect the yield components, the impact of water stress on the sunflower harvest index is complicated (Soriano et al., 2002). Global food security faces a 44% demand surge by 2050, challenged by abiotic and biotic stressors. Healthy soil, contributing up to 60% of crop yield, is crucial. Sustainable soil management and precision agriculture are essential to build resilient systems, ensuring food for a growing population while protecting the environment (Hayat et al., 2025).

According to Prabhudeva et al. (1998), sunflower plants' susceptibility to drought stress during the bud initiation phase had a greater negative impact on seed and biological yield than during the seed filling stage. Water stress typically results in fewer pods and seeds per unit area, which lowers soybean seed output (Specht et al., 2001).

Water stress affects a number of plant processes that affect yield. Yield intricately combines a number of these procedures. As a result, it is challenging to understand how plants acquire, combine, and exhibit the constantly shifting and ambiguous activities during the crop's whole life cycle. A number of factors related to plant growth interact to produce grain production.

Lack of water causes a significant decline in crop plant yield characteristics, most likely due to disruptions in leaf gas exchange characteristics, which not only

restrict the size of source and sink tissues but also affect phloem loading, assimilate translocation, and dry matter partitioning (Farooq et al., 2009).

PHYSIOLOGICAL RESPONSES

Effect of drought stress on Root-shoot signaling

In order to adjust to changing conditions and coordinate growth rate and behaviour, plants can transmit both positive and negative signals between their roots and shoots. In addition to limiting root growth and altering root dispersion, environmental stress can also have a negative impact on shoot growth and functioning through root-to-shoot signalling (Novák and Lipiec, 2012).

Numerous plant hormones, such as abscisic acid (ABA). It has been demonstrated that auxin, cytokinin's, ethylene, gibberellins, and other elements like pH regulate physiological processes by acting as signal molecules under varying environmental stressors (Schachtman and Goodger, 2008). It has long been known that abscisic acid (ABA) is a stronger molecular indication of root-to-shoot stress (Schachtman and Goodger, 2008). ABA is produced by the roots and transported to the shoot through the xylem during soil drying. There, inhibits leaf growth and closes stomata prior to noticeable alterations in the water and nutritional status of the leaves (Wang et al., 2000).

Under drought stress, roots use xylem to trigger a signal cascade that causes physiological changes in the shoots assessing the degree of stress adaption at last. Ethylene, malate, cytokinin's, and abscisic acid (ABA) have all been linked to root-shoot communication. An important adaptation to the field's limited water supply is stomatal closure, which is brought on by drought-induced root-to-leaf communication via the transpiration stream. ABA encourages potassium ion outflow from the guard cells, which lowers turgor pressure and causes stomata to close. Due to breakage of the cell membrane or loss of cell turgor, dehydration of plants has been shown to increase ABA levels by up to 50 times (Guerrero and Mullet, 1986).

Effects of composition drought stress on pigment

Plants need photosynthetic pigments mostly for light absorption and lowering power generation. According to Farooq et al. (2009), soil drying is a problem for

both chlorophyll a and b. Carotenoids, however, serve other purposes and give plants some resistance against drought's enemies. It found that education and experience don't predict familiarity with stomatal pathways or the use of molecular techniques like CRISPR-Cas9 and RNAi, which are widely adopted. The research emphasizes the need for targeted training in molecular methods and more diverse, realistic environmental stress treatments to better understand stomatal responses in fluctuating conditions (Sattar, et al., 2024).

Chlorophyll content

The ratio of carotenoids and chlorophyll "a" and "b" changed under drought stress (Anjum et al., 2003). Under water-limiting conditions, the Chl a: b ratio significantly decreased in both cultivars as the concentration of chlorophyll b rose in two lines of okra while chlorophyll a remained unchanged (Estill et al., 1991). Primary production can be directly limited by low quantities of photosynthetic pigments, which also affect photosynthetic potential. The amount of chlorophyll in leaves is a physiologic metric that is highly interesting in and of itself. Studies show that the majority of plants' chlorophyll loss in reaction to water deprivation happens in the mesophyll cells, while the bundle sheath cells lose less chlorophyll Carotenoids.

Carotenoids

All photosynthetic and many non-photosynthetic organisms de novo synthesize the broad class of isoprenoid compounds known as carotenoids (Andrew et al., 2008). Although they are an essential component of the antioxidant defense system of plants, carotenes are highly vulnerable to oxidative damage. All green plants' chloroplasts contain B-carotene, which is only bonded to the PSI and PSII core complexes (Havaux, 1998). Among other alterations, water stress can lower tissue concentrations of carotenoids and chlorophylls (Kiani et al., 2008), mainly through thylakoids' generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Reddy et al., 2004). These findings call for concentrated efforts to either modify the pathways involved in pigment biosynthesis or induce pigment synthesis in order to increase plants' resistance to drought.

Osmolyte accumulation

Different kinds of organic and inorganic solutes are accumulated by plants in the cytosol to reduce osmotic potential and assert cell (Rhodes and Samaras, 1994) Turgor. In reaction to the buildup of proline, sucrose, soluble carbohydrates, and other solutes in the cytoplasm, osmotic adjustment may also be used to maintain leaf turgor under drought stress, enhancing water uptake from drying soil. Osmotic adjustment is the method by which these solutes accumulate during drought stress, and it is highly dependent on the rate of plant water stress. Low levels of these suitable solutes are indicative of wheat and it was discovered that proline mobilization and accumulation increased resistance to water stress (Nayyar and Walia, 2003).

When plants experience water deficit stress, their initial reaction is to accumulate proline in an effort to lessen cell damage. Reformist Proline accumulated significantly in water-stressed maize plants under drought stress. (Anjum and others, 2011).

Proline can work as a signalling molecule to activate particular genes, affect cell division or death, and modify mitochondrial processes expression that may be crucial for plants to recover from stress (Szabados and Savoure', 2009). Proline concentration has been found to be generally higher in stress-tolerant plants than in stress-sensitive ones, and accumulation of proline during drought stress has been linked to stress tolerance in many plant species. It controls protein solvation, maintains complex proteins' quaternary structure, maintains membrane integrity under dehydration stress, and lessens lipid membrane oxidation or photoinhibition Turkan and Demiral (2004).

ANATOMICAL ADAPTATIONS

Cuticle Thickness

Water's distinct physical and chemical characteristics enable it to play a wide variety of biological roles and are crucial to the construction and operation of plants (Turner, 1981; Kramer, 1983). Water helps keep proteins, polysaccharides, and nucleic acids structurally sound (Almond & Sheehan, 2003).It also acts as a solvent for a range of ions, tiny molecules, and organic compounds, which explains how many substances dissolve inside cells (Moore, Clark, & Stern, 1995). Water can move substances through

plants by acting as a solvent, including sucrose, one of the main byproducts of photosynthesis (Lemoine, 2000).

Water makes up 90% of the fresh weight of herbaceous plants and 70% of the fresh weight of woody plants. It is also a component of the plant body, a coolant, and a reactant in photosynthesis (Almond & Sheehan, 2003). Consequently, it's critical for plants to be able to sustain water levels at sufficient levels for survival.

Semi-arid regions are prone to droughts and have little annual rainfall, often between 250 and 500 mm¹¹. One of the most extreme forms of plant stress is drought, which can cause desiccation, wilting, leaf abscission, and ultimately death, all of which can drastically lower plant output (McDowell et al., 2008). The enormous diversity of plant shape and growth forms frequently found in arid regions, however, is due to the fact that many species have adapted to live in such settings and withstand dry spells (Cowling, Esler, Midgley, & Honig, 1994).

Stomatal Structure (Sunken, stomata, crypts)

The stomatal apparatus's architectural features are crucial to its ability to prevent lethal water loss while permitting enough carbon acquisition. Stomata are the most significant plant-atmosphere interface throughout the light portion of the day because they dynamically balance a cuticle-sealed leaf's transpiration and photosynthesis rates. They are thought to maximize CO₂ influx for a specific physiologically acceptable water loss in an ideal mode (Cowan and Farquhar, 1977; Vico et al., 2013).

For many years, plant physiologists and anatomists have been interested in the location of stomata in relation to the leaf surface (Weyers and Meidner, 1990; Willmer, 1996; Larcher, 2001). In the majority of species, the variable stomatal hole, which is bounded by guard cells, is located under the hard ledges formed by the leaf cuticle covering all epidermal cells (Turner, 1994; Willmer, 1996). The guard cells' centre tip may protrude above, align with, or be sunken beneath the epidermis' surface in this general configuration. In the latter instance, guard cells form stomatal antechambers at the bottom of crypts, deep pits, or depressions.

Invaginations of the leaf epidermis that protrude into abaxial mesophyll tissue or complete leaf margins that

tightly coil toward the main vein can both create stomata in crypts. Their sizes and forms vary, allowing for an average of 40 stomata per crypt in fossils of *Banksia paleocarpa* (Carpenter et al., 2014) or as many as 35 stomata in a single crypt, as in six *Banksia* species studied by Hassiotou et al. (2009a).

A network of trichomes frequently fills the big crypts (about 300 μm in diameter), potentially hiding the pit's opening. The function of the crypts and hairs in preventing water loss is unclear (see below). In the Australian Proteaceae, crypts have undergone multiple evolutionary stages from both wet and supposedly dry regions (Jordan et al., 2008).

Most vascular plants have stomata in shallow epidermal depressions that are partially covered by cuticular ledges (papilla). They can take many various forms; for instance, papillae encircling the stomatal apparatus can give the appearance of sunken stomata in pits. The number of papillose-pitted species in the Proteaceae does not correlate with the degree of aridity in their environments.

Jordan et al. (2008) contend that, like trichomes in crypts and on the leaf surface, papillae and other epidermal characteristics that make the leaf surface rougher reduce its wettability. Reduced wettability

protects stomatal pits from waterlogging, and hairs may stop fungi from growing through the stomatal pore into the stomatal antechamber and the inside of the leaf. Species having a paracytic stomatal complex, which is defined by a lateral pair of subsidiary cells that arch over the stomatal pore to form a stomatal antechamber, may benefit most from these evolutionary advantages (Gray et al., 2020).

It is believed that the walls are cuticle-covered and do not serve as a substantial source of transpired water. *Nerium oleander* and other *Banksia* species are common examples of xerophilous or sclerophyllous species that thrive in arid environments and typically have crypts. For instance, the internal surface area of the crypts is five times larger than the crypt pore area, while the visible crypt holes (crypt pores) in *Banksia Ilic folia* make up around 20% of the total abaxial leaf surface area (Roth-Nebelsick et al., 2009).

As a result, the leaf area may be 100% larger than the estimated size due to the crypt walls. Recently, fossil needles of the gymnosperm *Cryptokerpia sarlaccophora* from Permian strata in Jordan were found to exhibit an intriguing, very noticeable kind of crypt (Blome Kemper et al., 2019).

Figure 2. Crypts with stomata and hairs in *Nerium oleander*. Cryo-scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of transects through the whole crypts on the abaxial side of an *N. oleander* leaf, with crypt walls, internal trichomes and trichomes overarching the crypt aperture (A, B). Details of the crypt interior showing numerous stomata at the crypt bottom (arrows in D, E) and fractured crypt walls. Hollow trichomes are protruding from the individual cells forming the wall (C, F).

Xylem vessels and lignification

Cell walls in terrestrial plants are mostly made of polysaccharides, such as pectin's, cellulose, and hemicelluloses. Secondary walls with intricate thickening patterns and impregnation with the polyphenolic polymer lignin strengthen the walls of certain cells, most notably the water conducting tracheids and vessel components of xylem tissues in

vascular plants. Both structural support for the entire plant and resistance to cell collapse under the stress of water transport were made possible by this evolutionary breakthrough. It has long been known that the competing architectural needs of water flow and mechanical support are reflected in the size and shape of conducting cells (Esau, 1953).

Table 1. Key Anatomical Adaptations in Plants Under Drought Conditions

Anatomical Feature	Function/Benefit	Examples
Thick Cuticle	Reduces water loss by minimizing transpiration	Xerophytes, succulents
Sunken Stomata	Traps moisture in pits, reducing transpiration rate	Nerium oleander, Banksia spp.
Stomatal Crypts	Provides a humid microenvironment for stomata, lowering water loss	Hakea, Banksia spp.
Multiple Epidermal Layers	Acts as a barrier against desiccation and heat stress	Cactus, desert shrubs
Mesophyll Compaction	Reduces intercellular spaces, limiting internal water vapor diffusion	Sclerophyllous leaves (Eucalyptus)
Thick Cell Walls	Maintains cell turgor and structural integrity under water-deficit conditions	Woody shrubs, evergreens
Trichomes (leaf hairs)	Reflects sunlight, traps humidity, and reduces leaf temperature	Lavandula, Artemisia spp.
Reduced Intercellular Spaces	Minimizes evaporative surfaces within the leaf	Xerophytes

DISCUSSION

A number of basic anatomical traits are shared by *Crassula* species, but as expected, those that originated in arid conditions had more adaptations that conserved water. Although the leaf epidermis of all species was uniseriate, the cuticles of the species found in arid regions were noticeably thicker. Furthermore, only these arid-adapted species showed secondary thickening. Succulent plants do not necessarily have many epidermises (Von Willert et al., 1992) perhaps because many of them can improve their water-use efficiency via CAM (Smith & Crouch, 2009). With the exception of *C. ovata*, which had a periderm, all species under investigation had uniseriate leaf and stem epidermides.

A barrier against water loss is provided by cuticles (Riederer & Schreiber, 2001). Because the adaxial surface of leaves is typically more susceptible to desiccation than the abaxial surface, its cuticles are frequently thicker (Eckardt, 2004). Because it is less likely to desiccate, *Crassula helmsii* has the thinnest leaf cuticles (Scott, 2008). It was discovered that the subtropical coast's *Crassula multicava* had the thickest

cuticles. In addition to preventing water loss, plant cuticles also provide protection from fungi, which may be crucial in a moist subtropical climate.

The stems *C. multicava* and *C. ovata* exhibited secondary thickening, which is probably crucial for bearing the weight of their succulent leaves (Von Willert et al., 1992). Secondary care is not necessary for *C. helmsii* or *C. Socialis* thickening for support since *C. socialis* has a compact growth form and *C. helmsii* is an aquatic species that can be sustained by water (Von Willert et al., 1992; Jayeola & Folerunso, 2009).

Along the gradient, trees were able to have a significant water transport capacity and minimal energy expenditure due to their large and dense xylem vessels. The question of whether vessel diameter and water flow are negatively correlated is still up for debate, primarily due to differing data from various plant species or PFTs. According to our observations, the vessel width in trees and annual grasses varied somewhat along the gradient, however it reduced in shrubs and perennial grasses as aridity increased. Shrubs and perennial grasses create narrow vessels to

improve water uptake and promote plant survival when water is short (Chen & Wang, 2009).

Because native annual grasses combine short life cycles and high rates of leaf gas exchange when using maximum water resources efficiently during rainy seasons¹, and because deep-rooted trees (i.e., the length of root > 3 m) could utilize soil moisture of the deep soil layer (Gui & Yan, 2009; Long & Tingxi, 2007) the differences in vessel diameter between annual grasses and trees were likely to be smaller. Thus, these results suggest that in the temperate grasslands along the large-scale gradient in northeastern China, aridity may not be the main factor influencing the anatomical structure of trees and annual grasses.

Plants' capacity for self-regulation and environmental adaptation is correlated with their leaf characteristics. The study of plant adaptation focuses on the responses and adaptations of leaf characteristics to climatic change. The main way that plants lose water is through transpiration of their leaves. The shape and anatomical structure of leaves, which are the most vulnerable organs in water-deficient environments, can provide a better indication of a plant's capacity to withstand drought stress (Ennajeh, Vadel, Cochard, & Khemira, 2010).

The current study demonstrated that plant leaf thickness and structure were correlated with genetics by comparing eight apple rootstocks under drought stress in terms of leaf thickness, upper epidermis thickness, palisade tissue thickness, and spongy tissue thickness. The ability of the thicker leaves to retain water is stronger (Aparecido, Miller, Cahill, & Moore, 2017).

The thicker upper epidermis and thicker leaves of Fupingqiuzi can effectively restrict transpiration and stop water from evaporating, making Fupingqiuzi more suited to the arid climate. These align with the findings of the examination of the membership function. Research has indicated that the greater the thickness of the palisade tissue, the smaller the cells are, the more tightly they are arranged, and the more resistant they are to drought (Zhang et al., 2015). Water is essential for plant development and metabolism, according to studies. Stronger water retention and drought tolerance are associated with increased relative water content during drought circumstances (Chakherchaman et al., 2009).

Water stress has a variety of consequences on plants' development and metabolism, but its most noticeable impact is on photosynthesis (Wang et al., 2018; Schapendonk, Spitters, & Groot, 1989). The primary pigment for photosynthesis, chlorophyll, is essential for the process's absorption of light. Additionally, its relative concentration is a significant predictor of growth and development stages, nutritional stress, and plant photosynthetic ability (Pavlovic et al., 2015). Carotenoids stop plants from absorbing light energy in a reasonable manner and help to coordinate photosynthesis by capturing light energy and defending against light damage (Hashimoto, Uragami, & Cogdell, 2016).

In order for plants to cope with drought stress, osmotic adjustment is crucial (Zivcak, Brestic, & Sytar, 2016). Studies have shown that during drought stress, starch breakdown was accelerated, increasing the amount of soluble sugar and enhancing plant tolerance to drought (Du et al., 2020; Jia et al., 2021). One of the key components in plant osmotic regulation is plant NSC content. Their level of accumulation is correlated with plants' resistance to drought stress, and they have a specific impact on osmotic control. By increasing their osmotic potential through the accumulation of NSC content, plants may withstand dry stress.

The findings of earlier research (Couchoud et al., 2019; Comas et al., 2013) shown that the membrane structure of roots was harmed to differing degrees under various drought stress circumstances; the more severe the drought stress, the more serious the damage to the membrane structure, and the higher the relative conductivity. The eight rootstocks in this study showed an increase in relative conductivity during drought stress, suggesting that the cell membranes of the various rootstocks suffered some degree of damage during drought stress. Pakistan's livestock sector is vital, contributing significantly to the economy and employment. However, it faces environmental challenges. Sustainable practices like utilizing diverse forages and implementing three-strata forage systems are crucial. These approaches enhance animal health, improve soil fertility and carbon sequestration, and offer economic benefits by reducing reliance on expensive concentrates, ultimately fostering a resilient and sustainable agricultural future (Hayat et al., 2025).

CONCLUSION

To sum up, the comparative study of plant morphology, anatomy, and physiology shows that drought tolerance is a complicated characteristic controlled by a variety of structural and functional adaptations. In terms of anatomy, drought-tolerant plants frequently have larger leaves, smaller stomata, improved palisade tissue, and fully formed vascular systems that facilitate effective water transport and retention. During times of limited availability, morphological traits like waxy cuticles, reduced leaf area, and deep root systems greatly aid in maximizing water intake and limiting water loss. Physiological processes that support plant growth during drought stress include osmotic adjustment, elevated antioxidant activity, effective photosynthetic responses, and preservation of cell membrane stability. Plants' genetic composition, ecotype, and interactions with their surroundings all have a significant impact on their capacity to endure and thrive in water-deficit situations. In light of global climate change and growing water shortages, this research not only broadens our understanding of plant adaptation techniques but also offers important insights for breeding and creating crop types that are resistant to drought.

REFERENCES

- Almond, A., Sheehan, J.K. (2003) Predicting the molecular shape of polysaccharides from dynamic interactions with water. *Glycobiology* 13: 255- 264.
- Andrew J.S., Moreau, H., Kuntz, M., Pagny, G., Lin, C., Tanksley, S., and McCarthy, J. (2008). An investigation of carotenoid biosynthesis in *Coffea canephora* and *Coffea arabica*. *J. Plant Physiol.*, 165:1087-1106.
- Anjum, F., Yaseen, M., Rasul, E., Wahid, A., and Anjum, S.(2003b). Water stress in barley (*Hordeum vulgare*L.). II. Effect on chemical composition and chlorophyll contents. *Pakistan J. Agric. Sci.*, 40:45 49.
- Anjum, S. A., Ashraf, U., Tanveer, M., Khan, I., Hussain, S., Shahzad, B., Zohaib, A., Abbas, F., Saleem, M. F., Ali, I. (2017). Drought induced changes in growth, osmolyte accumulation and antioxidant metabolism of three maize hybrids. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 8, 69.
- Anjum, S.A., Wang, L.C., Farooq, M., Khan, I., Xue, L.L. (2011b). Methyl jasmonate-induced alteration in lipid peroxidation, antioxidative defense system and yield in soybean under drought. *J. Agron. Crop Sci.*, doi:10.1111/j.1439-037X.2010.00468.
- Aparecido, L.M.T., Miller, G.R., Cahill, A.T., Moore, G.W. (2017). Leaf surface traits and water storage retention affect photosynthetic responses to leaf surface wetness among wet tropical forest and semiarid savanna plants. *Tree Physiology*, 37:1285–300.
- Blomenkemper, P., Abu Hamad, A., Bomfleur, B. (2019). *Cryptokerpia sarlaccophora* gen. et sp. nov., an enigmatic plant fossil from the Late Permian Umm Irna Formation of Jordan. *Palz* 93: 479–485.
- Carpenter, R.J., McLoughlin, S., Hill, R.S., McNamara, K.J., Jordan, G.J. (2014). Early evidence of xeromorphy in angiosperms: stomatal encryption in a new eocene species of *Banksia* (Proteaceae) from Western Australia. *American Journal of Botany* 101: 1486–1497.
- Chakherchaman, S., Arbat, H.K., Yarnia, M., Mostafaei, H., Hassanpanah, D. (2009). Study on relations between relative water content, cell membrane stability and duration of growth period with grain yield of lentil genotypes under drought stress and non-stress conditions. *International Meeting on Soil Fertility Land Management and Agroclimatology*. Turkey, pp. 749–55.
- Chen, L. & Wang, R. Z. (2009). Anatomical and physiological divergences and compensatory effects in two *Leymus chinensis* (Poaceae) ecotypes in northeast China. *Agr. Ecosyst. Environ.* 134, 46–52.

- Comas, L.H., Becker, S.R., Cruz, V.M.V., Byrne, P.F., Dierig, D.A. (2013). Root traits contributing to plant productivity under drought. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 4:442.
- Couchoud, M., Der, C., Girodet, S., Vernoud, V., Prudent, M., Leborgne-Castel, N. (2019). Drought stress stimulates endocytosis and modifies membrane lipid order of rhizodermal cells of *Medicago truncatula* in a genotype-dependent manner. *BMC Plant Biology*, 19:221.
- Cowan, I.R., Farquhar, G.D. (1977). Stomatal function in relation to leaf metabolism and environment. *Symposia of the Society for Experimental Biology*, 31: 471–505.
- Cowling, R.M., Esler, K.J., Midgley, G.F., Honig, M.A. (1994) Plant functional diversity, species diversity and climate in arid and semi-arid southern Africa. *J Arid Environ*, 27: 141–158.
- Demiral, T., Turkan, I. (2004). Does exogenous glycinebetaine affect antioxidative system of rice seedlings under NaCl treatment? *J. Plant Physiol.*, 161:1089-1110.
- Du, Y., Zhao, Q., Chen, L., Yao, X., Zhang, W. (2020). Effect of drought stress on sugar metabolism in leaves and roots of soybean seedlings. *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry*, 146:1–12.
- Eckardt, N.A. (2004) The role of PHANTASTICA in leaf development. *Plant Cell*, 16: 1073–1075.
- Ennajeh M., Vadel, A.M., Cochard, H., Khemira, H. (2010). Comparative impacts of water stress on the leaf anatomy of a drought-resistant and a drought-sensitive olive cultivar. *The Journal of Horticultural Science and Biotechnology*, 85:289–94.
- Esau, K. (1953) *Plant Anatomy* (Wiley, New York).
- Escalona, J. M., Flexas, J., & Medrano, H. (1999). Stomatal and non-stomatal limitations of photosynthesis under water stress in field-grown grapevines. *Australian Journal of Plant Physiology*, 27(6), 421–433.
- Estill, K., Delaney, R.H., Smith, W.K., and Ditterline, R.L. (1991). Water relations and productivity of alfalfa leaf chlorophyll variants. *Crop Sci.*, 31:1229-1233.
- Farooq, M., Wahid, A., Kobayashi, N., Fujita, D., Basra, S.M.A. (2009). Plant drought stress: effects, mechanisms and management. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.*, 29:185-212.
- Farooq, M., Wahid, A., Kobayashi, N., Fujita, D., Basra, S.M.A. (2009). Plant drought stress: effects, mechanisms and management. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.*, 29:185-212
- Gaspar, T., Franck, T., Bisbis, B., Kevers, C., Jouve, L., Hausman J.F. and Dommes, J. 2002. Concepts in plant stress physiology. Application to plant tissue cultures. *Plant Growth Regul.*, 37:263- 285.
- Gray, A., Liu, L., Facette, M. (2020). Flanking support: how subsidiary cells contribute to stomatal form and function. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 11: 881.
- Guerrero, F., Mullet, J.E. (1986). Increased abscisic acid biosynthesis during plant dehydration requires transcription. *Plant Physiol.*, 80:588-591.
- Gui, Q. X. & Yan, L. (2009). Roots distribution of three desert shrubs and their response to precipitation under co-occurring conditions. *Acta Ecologica Sinica* 29(1), 130–137.
- Harris, D., Tripathi, R.S., Joshi, A. (2002). On-farm seed priming to improve crop establishment and yield in dry direct-seeded rice, in: Pandey S., Mortimer M., Wade L., Tuong T.P., Lopes K., Hardy B. (Eds.), *Direct seeding: Research Strategies and Opportunities*, International Research Institute, Manila, Philippines, pp. 231- 240.
- Hashimoto, H., Uragami, C., Cogdell, R.J. (2016). Carotenoids and photosynthesis. In *Carotenoids in Nature. Subcellular Biochemistry*, eds. Stange C. vol 79. Switzerland: Springer, Cham. pp. 111–39.
- Hassiotou, F., Evans, J.R., Ludwig, M., Veneklaas, E.J. (2009a). Stomatal crypts may facilitate diffusion of CO₂ to adaxial mesophyll cells in thick sclerophylls. *Plant, Cell & Environment* 32: 1596–1611.
- Havaux, M. (1998). Carotenoids as membrane stabilizers in chloroplasts. *Trends Plant Sci.*, 3:147–151.

- Hayat, M. K., Mumtaz, M. M., Ali, M. A., Huaira, A., Rehman, M. N. U., Shabbir, M. A., ... & Afzal, A. (2024). Optimizing Livestock Feed Systems: A Multi-faceted Approach for Sustainable and Resilient Animal Agriculture; A comprehensive review. *Journal of Plant Biota*, 27.
- Hayat, M. K., Khan, A. R., Klutse, S., Rasool, M. W., & Mohsin, M. (2025). Empowering Crops: How Organic, Agronomic Practices and Technology Can Fortify Our Fields. *World News of Natural Sciences*, 59, 358-383.
- Hussain, M., Malik, M.A., Farooq, M., Ashraf, M.Y., Cheema, M.A. (2008). Improving drought tolerance by exogenous application of glycine betaine and salicylic acid in sunflower. *J. Agron. Crop Sci.*, 194: 193-199.
- Jayeola, A.A., Folerunso, E.A. (2009) Ecological anatomy of some hydrophytes in Nigeria. *Afr J Biotechnol*, 8: 3377- 3381.
- Jia, X., Jia, X., Li, T., Wang, Y., Sun, X. (2021). MdATG5a induces drought tolerance by improving the antioxidant defenses and promoting starch degradation in apple. *Plant Science*, 312:111052.
- Jordan, G.J., Weston, P.H., Carpenter, R.J., Dillon, R.A., Brodribb, T.J. (2008). The evolutionary relations of sunken covered, and encrypted stomata to dry habitats in proteaceae. *American Journal of Botany*, 95: 521-530.
- Kaya, M.D., Okçub, G., Ataka, M., Çikilic, Y., Kolsarıca, Ö. (2006) Seed treatments to overcome salt and drought stress during germination in sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*L.). 24:291-295
- Khan, M. A., Iqbal, M., Akram, M., Ahmad, M., Hassan, M. W., & Jamil, M. (2013). Recent advances in molecular tool development for drought tolerance breeding in cereal crops: A review. *Zemdirbyste-Agriculture*, 100(3), 325-334.
- Kiani, S.P., Maury, P., Sarrafi, A., and Grieu, P. (2008). QTL analysis of chlorophyll fluorescence parameters in sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) under well-watered and water-stressed conditions. *Plant Sci.*, 175: 565-573.
- Larcher, W. (2001). *Physiological plant ecology*. Berlin Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag.
- Lemoine, R. (2000) Sucrose transporters in plants: update on function and structure. *Biochim Biophys Acta Biomembr* 1465: 246 -262.
- Li, W., Wang, Y., Zhang, Y., Wang, R., & Xie, Z. (2020). Impacts of drought stress on the morphology, physiology, and sugar content of Lanzhou lily (*Lilium davidii* var. *unicolor*). *Acta Physiologiae Plantarum*, 42, 127.
- Long, M. & Tingxi, L. (2007) Relationship of plant ecotype with groundwater depth and soil moisture in Horqin sandy land. *J. Desert Res.* 27(3), 391-396.
- McDowell, N., Pockman, W.T., Allen, C.D. et al. (2008) Mechanisms of plant survival and mortality during drought: why do some plants survive while others succumb to drought? *New Phytologist* 178: 719- 739.
- Misra, V., Solomon, S., Mall, A. K., Prajapati, C. P., Hashem, A., Abd Allah, E. F., & Ansari, M. I. (2020). Morphological assessment of water stressed sugarcane: A comparison of waterlogged and drought affected crop. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 27(1), 1228-1236.
- Moore, R., Clark, W.D., Stern, K.R. (1995) *Botany*. Dubuque: Wm. C. Brown Publishers.
- Nayyar, H., Walia, D.P. (2003). Water stress induced proline accumulation in contrasting wheat genotypes as affected by calcium and abscisic acid. *Biol. Plant.*, 46:275-279.
- Nonami, H. (1998). Plant water relations and control of cell elongation at low water potentials. *J. Plant Res.*, 111:373-382.
- Novák, V., and Lipiec, J. (2012). Water extraction by roots under environmental stresses. In: *Pollution and Water Resources*, Columbia University Seminar Proceedings: Impact of Anthropogenic Activity and Climate Changes on the Environment of Central Europe and USA (Eds J. Halasi-Kun, V. Stekauerová, I. Fodor, V. Nagy, B. Sinóros-Szabó, R. Lo Pinto). Slovak Academy of Sciences - Hungarian Academy of Sciences - Columbia University.

- Patmi, Y. S., Pitoyo, A., Solichatun, & Sutarno. (2020). Effect of drought stress on morphological, anatomical, and physiological characteristics of Cempo Ireng Cultivar Mutant Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) strain 51 irradiated by gamma-ray. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1436, 012015.
- Pavlovic, D., Nikolic, B., Djurovic, S., Waisi, H., Andjelkovic, A. (2015). Chlorophyll as a measure of plant health: Agroecological aspects. *Pesticidi i Fitomedicina*, 29:21–34.
- Prabhudeva, T.V., Chalapathi, M.M., Thimmegowda, S., Devakumar, N., Rao, G.G., and Mallikarjuna, K. (1998). Soil moisture stress and drought susceptibility index in sunflower. *Indian Agric.*, 42:287-289.
- Reddy, A.R., Chaitanya, K.V. and Vivekanandan, M. (2004). Drought induced responses of photosynthesis and antioxidant metabolism in higher plants. *J. Plant Physiol.*, 161:189-1202.
- Reiderer, M., Schreiber, L. (2001) Protecting against water loss: analysis of the barrier properties of plant cuticles. *J Exp Bot*, 52: 2023 –2032.
- Rhodes, D., Samaras, Y. (1994). Genetic control of osmoregulation in plants. In cellular and molecular physiology of cell volume regulation. Strange, K. Boca Raton: CRC Press, pp. 347-361.
- Rollins, J.A., Habte, E., Templer, S.E., Colby, T., Schmidt, J., and Von Korff, M. (2013). Leaf proteome alterations in the context of physiological and morphological responses to drought and heat stress in barley (*Hordeum vulgare*L.). *J.Exp. Botany*, 64:3201-3212.
- Roth-Nebelsick, A., Hassiotou, F., Veneklaas, E.J. 2009. Stomatal crypts have small effects on transpiration: a numerical model analysis. *Plant Physiology*, 151: 2018–2027.
- Schachtman, D.P., and Goodger, J.Q.D., (2008). Chemical root to shoot signaling under drought. *Trends Plant Sci.*, 13:281-287.
- Schapendonk, A.H.C.M., Spitters, C.J.T., Groot, P.J. (1989). Effects of water stress on photosynthesis and chlorophyll fluorescence of five potato cultivars. *Potato Research*, 32:17–32.
- Sattar, M., Shabbir, M., Ullah, G., Abbas, K., Hussain, A., Hayat, M. K., ... & Usman, H. (2024). Molecular Mechanisms in Plant Physiology: Regulating Stomatal Development and Function Under Environmental Stress. *Frontiers in Health Informatics*, 13(8).
- Scott, P. (2008) *Physiology and Behavior of Plants*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons Ltd
- Smith, G.F., Crouch, N.R. (2009) *Guide to Succulents of Southern Africa*. Cape Town: Struck Nature.
- Soriano, M.A., Villalobos, F.J., and Fereres, E. (2002). Stress timing effects on sunflower harvest index. In: Villalobos, F.J., and Testi (Eds.), *L. VII Congress of the European Society for Agronomy*, pp: 141-2. Sevilla, Spain JA, Consejería de Agricultura y Pesca.
- Specht, J.E., Chase, K., Macrander, M., Graef, G.L., Chung, J., Markwell, J.P., Germann, M., Orf, J.H., and Lark, K.G. (2001). Soybean response to water. A QTL analysis of drought tolerance. *Crop Sci.*, 41:493-509.
- Szabados, L., Savoure, A. (2009). Proline: a multifunctional amino acid. *Trends Plant Sci.*, 15: 89-97.
- Taiz, L., & Zeiger, E. (2015). *Plant physiology and development* (6th ed.). Sinauer Associates.
- Taiz, L., Zeiger, E. (2006) *Plant Physiology*, 4th Ed., Sinauer Associates Inc. Publishers, Massachusetts.
- Turner, I.M. (1994). Sclerophylly: primarily protective? *Functional Ecology* 8: 669–675.
- Von Willert, D.J., Eller, B.M., Werger, M.J.A., Brinckmann, E., Ihlenfeldt, H.D. (1992) *Life Strategies of Succulents in Deserts: With Special Reference to the Namib Desert*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Von Willert, D.J., Eller, B.M., Werger, M.J.A., Brinckmann, E., Ihlenfeldt, H.D. (1992) *Life Strategies of Succulents in Deserts: With Special Reference to the Namib Desert*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Wang, Z., Li, G., Sun, H., Ma, L., Guo, Y. (2018). Effects of drought stress on photosynthesis and photosynthetic electron transport chain in young apple tree leaves. *Biology open* 7:bio035279.

- Wang, Z., Xiong, Y., and Wang, M., (2000). Study on expert system of irrigation forecast and decision making for water saving. Institute of Agricultural Soil Water Engineering of North West Science and Technology University of Agriculture Forestry, Yangling, Shaanxi.
- Werner, C., Correia, O., & Beyschlag, W. (1999). Two different strategies of Mediterranean macchia plants to avoid photoinhibitory damage by excessive radiation levels during summer drought. *Acta Oecologica*, 20(1), 15-23.
- Weyers, J.D.B., Meidner, H. (1990). *Methods in stomatal research*. Harlow, UK: Longman Group.
- Willmer, C.M., Fricker, M. (1996). *Stomata*. London: Chapman & Hall.
- Zhang, F., Zhang, K., Du, C., Li, J., Xing, Y. (2015). Effect of drought stress on anatomical structure and chloroplast ultrastructure in leaves of sugarcane. *Sugar Tech*, 17:41-48.
- Zivcak, M., Brestic, M., Sytar, O. (2016). Osmotic adjustment and plant adaptation to drought stress. In *Drought Stress Tolerance in Plants*, eds. Hossain M, Wani S, Bhattacharjee S, Burritt D, Tran LS. Vol 1. pp. 105-43. Switzerland: Springer, Cham.

